

The Influence Of The Time Token Model On The Social Science Learning Outcomes Of Class IV Students Of Private Primary School 125138 Pematang Siantar

Geneva New Year Manurung, Osco Parmonangan Sijabat, Sukardo Sitohang
Universitas HKBP Nomensen Pematang Siantar, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Geneva New Year Manurung;
irenarajagukguk20@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Time Token Model,
Learning Results.
Abstract

Received : 9, July

Revised : 20, August

Accepted: 23, September

©2023Manurung, Sijabat, Sitohang:
This is an open-access article distributed
under the terms of the [Creative
Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This research aims to find out whether the use of the Time Token Model has an influence on the learning outcomes of Class IV Students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar on theme 3 Caring for Living Creatures with sub-theme 1 Animals and Plants in My Home Environment in lesson 1 at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar. There are 2 hypotheses in this research, namely (1) there is an influence of the Time Token Model user on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class IV Students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar (H_a) and there is no influence of the Time Token Model on the Social Sciences Learning Results of Class IV Students of SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar (H_0). Pre-Experimental Design research type that uses a One Group Pretest-Posttest Research Design. The population of this study was all fourth grade students at SD Negeri 125238 Pematang Siantar, totaling 30 students. Data collection was carried out using test and observation techniques. This research data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the t count is 15.112 with a significance level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Time Token Model on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class IV Students at State Elementary School 125138 Pematang Siantar sub theme 1 animals and plants in my home environment means that H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the main means of improving the quality of human resources. Without education, it will be difficult to obtain maximum quality results from human resources. Education is the direction given by adults to the development of children to reach maturity with the aim of ensuring that children can carry out their life tasks on their own without the help of others (Feni 2014: 13).

In order for educational goals to be achieved, it is necessary to create a conducive atmosphere in the learning process so that students are truly interested and actively participate in the process. As described in PP no. 19 of 2005 concerning National education standards Article 19 Paragraph 1 namely "The learning process in educational units is carried out in an interactive, inspiring, fun, challenging manner, motivating students to participate actively and providing sufficient space for initiative, creativity and independence in accordance with the students' talents, interests and physical and psychological development."

Apart from the government's efforts to improve the quality of education, the contribution of teaching staff is also urgently needed, namely to improve the quality of learning, one of which is by implementing innovative learning so that learning becomes more effective and efficient. At the basic education level there are 8 subjects that must be taught in accordance with the subjects regulated in Permendiknas No.1. Decree No. 22 of 2006 stipulates that the SD/MI curriculum consists of 8 core subjects. In order to achieve national education goals, the government has carried out improvements and improvements in the quality of education at various levels. However, the facts in the field has not shown maximum results. One of the problems facing the world Our education is a problem of weak learning processes.

However, the facts on the ground do not show maximum results. One of the problems faced in our world of education is the problem of weak learning processes. In the learning process, students are less encouraged to develop thinking skills. The learning process in class is only directed at children's ability to memorize information, without being required to understand the information they remember to relate it to everyday life. The teacher's teaching and learning system must strive to ensure that the teaching and learning process reflects two directions, namely not just providing information without developing mental, physical abilities and personal appearance. However, the teaching and learning process in the classroom must be able to develop students' learning methods to acquire, manage, use and communicate in everyday life now and in the future. In carrying out learning in the classroom, teachers must be able to choose the right learning model or strategy, because the way the teacher chooses the right model or strategy greatly influences the smoothness of the learning process and student learning outcomes. Not all students in teaching and learning activities are able to concentrate for a long time.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The learning model is the entire series of presentation of teaching material which includes all aspects before and after learning carried out by the teacher as well as all related facilities which are used directly or indirectly in the teaching and learning process. The following will explain what the meaning of learning models is according to the opinions of experts. According to Joyce, Well, and Calhoun (Warsono and Hariyanto, 2013: 172) a learning model is a description of the learning environment, including the behavior the teacher applies in learning. Then, according to Udin (Hermawan, 2006:3) a learning model is a conceptual framework that describes systematic procedures in organizing learning experiences to achieve certain learning goals.

The cooperative learning model is a form of learning in which students learn and work in small groups collaboratively whose members consist of four to six people with a heterogeneous group structure. According to Nurulhayati (2002:25), cooperative learning is a learning strategy that involves student participation in a small group to interact with each other. Then, according to Anita Lie (2008:34), cooperative learning is learning that provides students with the opportunity to work together in carrying out structured tasks. Thus cooperative learning is learning that allows students to work together on structured tasks.

There are many types of cooperative learning models, including the Time Token learning type. This learning model is cooperative learning which was developed by adding talking coupons during learning. Which can be expected to motivate students to learn. The following will explain what the time token model means according to the opinions of experts. According to Eliyana (Shoimin, 2019:216), Time Token is a type of cooperative learning. Students are formed into study groups, which in this lesson teaches social skills to avoid students dominating the conversation or preventing students from remaining completely silent during discussions. Then, according to Rahmat Widodo (2009), the Time Token learning model is very appropriate for learning structures that can be used to teach social skills, to avoid students dominating conversations or students remaining completely silent.

The advantages of the Time Token Learning Model according to Istarani (2011:194) are:

1. Can increase the courage to stand in public.
2. Train students to express opinions correctly to others.
3. Train students to be disciplined and organized in speaking in front of people.

The disadvantages of the Time Token Model are:

Only prioritize students' speaking abilities. Generally, people who are good at speaking forget to write so that when they are able to speak they are considered to be smart students. only has the ability to speak, while his knowledge is not necessarily what other people imagine about him.

METHODS

This research is experimental research, namely pre-experimental design type. This research is experimental research, namely One Group Pretest-Posttest Design type . With this research, the results of the treatment can be known more accurately, because it can be compared with the situation before treatment and after treatment. This research was conducted at SD Negeri 125138 Jalan Medan Simpang Kerang, Sumber Jaya 1 Village, Pematang Siantar City, North Sumatra. This research was carried out in the even semester of FY 2023/2024. The researcher chose this location because to the researcher's knowledge no one had conducted research with the same title at that school. The population in this study were all fourth grade students at SD Negeri 125138 Jalan Medan Simpang Kerang, Sumber Jaya 1 Village, Pematang Siantar City, totaling 30 people. The instrument used in this research is a test instrument. The written test instrument is a multiple choice test. The test consists of 30 questions. To determine the feasibility of the test to be tested, researchers use validity tests, reliability tests, level of difficulty and distinguishing power . The data analysis techniques used in this research are:

- Normality test
To test whether the test scores are normally distributed or not, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov-Shapiro normality test is used
- Homogeneity Test
Apart from checking the normal distribution of data in a sample, researchers need to check the similarity (homogeneity) of several parts of the sample, to see whether the samples were taken from the same population. Testing sample homogeneity is a generalization for research results where research data is taken from separate groups originating from one population.
- Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine whether there are significant average differences in data. The hypothesis test used in this research is the t-test. Researchers used SPSS Windows 21, the t-test used was the paired sample t-test. The criteria for determining the significance of data are data with a probability of significance > 0.05 , then H_0 is accepted. Data with a probability of significance < 0.05 then H_0 is rejected.

To determine the decision rule, namely:

- a. If $t_{\text{Count}} > t_{\text{Table}}$ then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, meaning that the Time Token Model has an effect on student learning outcomes in the sub-theme Caring for Living Creatures class IV SD Negeri 125138 Jl. Medan Sp. Kerang Kel. Sumber Jaya 1 Pematang Siantar City.
- b. If $t_{\text{Count}} < t_{\text{Table}}$ then H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected, meaning that the Time Token Model has no effect on student learning outcomes in the sub-theme Caring for Living Creatures class IV SD Negeri 125138 Jl. Medan Sp. Kerang Kel. Sumber Jaya 1 Pematang Siantar City. Determine the t table price.
- c. Look for the t table using the t distribution table with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $dk = N - 1$.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This research is a pre-experimental design research with a one group pretest posttest design. Where students are given a pretest and posttest. The pretest is given before the treatment, the aim is to find out the initial condition of the students before being given the treatment. The posttest is given after the learning material is given using the Time Token Model, the aim is to find out the final condition of the students given the treatment.

Testing is carried out by calculating the calculated r value if the calculated r value of the instrument can be used for data collection, and the instrument used for data collection by researchers uses validation with a significant level using validation with a level of 5% or 0.05 where 30 levels. Based on the Excel results, it was found that the number of questions that could be used for the next question was 25 questions.

From the results of the reliability test calculations, it can be concluded that the results of the reliability test for this research are 0.90 (can be said to be reliable). Analysis of the level of difficulty of the test items is used to test the test questions in terms of their difficulty so that it can be obtained which questions fall into the difficult, medium and easy categories (it can be said that difficult questions = 5, medium questions = 24, easy questions = 1). The discriminating power of the questions is the ability of the questions to differentiate between groups of students with high and low scores. To calculate the differentiating power, the tests are grouped into two, namely the upper group and the lower group.

This descriptive analysis is used to describe the data from each research variable. The independent variable in this research is the Time Token learning model, while the dependent variable in this research is the student learning outcomes in social studies subjects in theme 3 sub theme 1 in class IV of SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar.

The normality test is intended to find out whether the data used is distributed or not. The homogeneity test is used to determine whether several population variants are the same or not. This test was carried out as a requirement in the independent sample t test and anova analysis. A homogeneity test is very necessary before comparing two or more groups, so that the differences that exist are not caused by basic differences (inhomogeneity of the groups being compared).

Testing this hypothesis using the t test is used to test the level of significance of the influence of the independent variable partially on the dependent variable. The test is carried out by comparing the t count > t table and significant values for the dependent variable. Basis for collecting decisions:

- a. If $\text{sig} > 0.05$ then the data is normally distributed
- b. If $\text{sig} < 0.05$ then the data is not distributed

that $t = 14.889$ with a significant level (2-tailed) of 0.000, significant probability < 0.05 , $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table} = 14.889 > 2.045$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the Time Token Model on the learning outcomes of class IV students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar.

In this section, the results found in the research that have been carried out will be described. The results in question are the conclusions drawn based on the data collected and the data analysis that has been carried out. Based on the pretest results, the average student learning outcome score was 52.63 with all students scoring below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Time Token Model was relatively low.

Furthermore, the average value of the posttest results was 82.87. So, after using the Time Token Model students have better learning outcomes than before using the Time Token Model. After carrying out the pretest and posttest normality tests, homogeneity was carried out. Based on the homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.057 was obtained. Based on the criteria that have been determined, if the sig value > 0.05 then the data is said to have homogeneous variation. In this case it can be seen that $0.057 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the data has the same characteristics or is homogeneous.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the data presented in the previous section, the researcher concluded that the student learning outcomes before being given treatment, all students still had not reached the KKM, namely 30 students (100%) and after being given treatment, student learning outcomes increased, namely 30 students (100%). % has a value above the KKM and is based on the

results of hypothesis testing with a significance level = 0.05 and t table of 2.045, t count of 14.889. Thus ($t \text{ count} > t \text{ table } 14.889 > 2.045$), it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Time Token Model on the learning outcomes of class IV students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar.

REFERENCES

- Arikunto Suharsimi, 2013. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Apriyani Br Sembiring, Darinda Sofia Tanjung, Patri Janson Silaban. 2021. *Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Time Token Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa Sekolah Dasar pada Pembelajaran Tematik*. Vol. 5(5): hal. 3.
- Dimyanti dan Mudjiono, Suprijono, Amir dan Risnawati. 2017. *Perpustakaan UniversitasIslamRiau*.
(file:///C:/Users/Personal/Downloads/Documents/bab2.pdf, diakses 2017).
- Fadillah Ahmad. 2016. *Analisis Minat Belajar Dan Bakat Terhadap Hasil Belajar Matematika Siswa*. *Jurnal Matematika dan Pendidikan Matematika*. Vol.1 (2): Hal.115.
- Fitri Herwati Isna. 2020. *Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Time Token Untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Berbicara Siswa Pada Tema Peristiwa Dalam Kehidupan Di Kelas V MI AL-Hidayah Pekan Baru*. Pekanbaru: Fakultas Tarbiyah dan Keguruan.
- Hamdani. 2011. *Strategi Belajar Mengajar*. Bandung: Cv Pustaka Setia.
- Hamzah B.Uno. 2007. *Model Pembelajaran Menciptakan Proses Belajar Mengajar Yang Kreatif Dan Efektif*. Jakarta: Bumi Akasara.
- Hartoto Tri. 2016. "Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Grup Investigation (GI) Meningkatkan Aktivitas Dan Hasil Belajar". *Jurnal HISTORIA*. Vol. 4(2): Hal. 135.
- Hayati S. Belajar Dam Pembelajaran Berbasis Cooperative Learning. Magelang. Istarani. 2011. *Model Pembelajaran Inovatif*. Medan: Media persada.
- Maulida. 2016. *Pengaruh Penerapan Metode Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Time Token Trens Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Pada Materi Pasar Di Kelas VIII SMP Negeri 2 Kutablang Kabupaten Bireuen*. Vol. 4(1): Hal. 14.

- Ni Md. Tita Tamara. 2019. Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Time Token Berbantuan Media Audio Visual Terhadap Hasil Belajar IPS Vol.2 no.1
- Ni Made Eva Suryantari, I Nengah Suadnyana, I Gusti Agung Ayu Wulandari. 2018. Pengaruh Model Time Token Berbasis Tri Hita Karana Terhadap Kompetensi Pengetahuan IPA Siswa Kelas IV. Vol.1, No.2.
- Octavia, A Shilpy. 2020. Model-Model Pembelajaran. Yogyakarta: CV Budi Utama.
- Rahmawati, Kurnia Dwi. 2017. Analisis Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe STAD Dalam Pembelajaran Tematik di Kelas IV SD Muhammadiyah 4 Malang. Skripsi Tidak Diterbitkan. Malang: FKIP Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang.
- Rusman. 2010. Model-model Pembelajaran. Jakarta: PT Rajagrafindo Persada.
- Slameto, Dalyono Syah. 2018. Pengertian Belajar. Magelang.
- Slameto. 2018. Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Hasil Belajar. Magelang.
- Shoimin Aris. 2013. 68 Model Pembelajaran Inovatif Dalam Kurikulum 2013. Yogyakarta: AR-RUZZ Media.
- Supardi, Trianto, Djahiri. 2017. Universitas Kristen Satya Wacana. Kutowinangun.
- Sugiyono, 2017. Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.